

PERSONALITY TRAITS AND ONLINE EXPERIENCES AMONG GRADUATE SCHOOL STUDENTS AT WENZHOU UNIVERSITY

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Personality Traits and Online Experiences among Graduate School Students at Wenzhou University

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Abstract

This study, "Personality Traits and Online Experiences among Graduate Students at Wenzhou University," examines how personality traits influence graduate students' online learning experiences. Positioned within the ongoing shift toward digital education accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, the research explores how traits like openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and emotional stability impact student engagement, satisfaction, and adaptability in online settings. Focusing on Wenzhou University, the study highlights notable differences in online learning experiences based on personality. Findings reveal that students high in openness and conscientiousness report greater engagement and course satisfaction, while extraverted and agreeable students benefit from interactive, community-focused elements. Those with high conscientiousness especially value structured content, which aids their time management and focus. Conversely, challenges such as technical issues and feelings of isolation negatively impact concentration and motivation. The study suggests integrating flexible course features, technical support, and mental health resources to support varied personality needs, fostering a more inclusive and resilient online learning environment.

Keywords: *personality traits, online learning, graduate students, engagement, adaptation*

Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology and the increasing prevalence of online learning have transformed the global education landscape, particularly in higher education. Across the world, universities and other educational institutions are shifting to digital platforms to facilitate flexible learning environments that transcend geographical barriers. This transition has prompted a growing body of research examining the factors that contribute to students' success in online learning. Personality traits have emerged as one key area of interest, as they can significantly influence students' attitudes, behaviors, and outcomes in digital learning contexts (Li & Tsai, 2017). Studies conducted in various countries indicate that personality dimensions, such as extroversion, conscientiousness, and openness to experience, affect how students engage with online learning platforms, their motivation levels, and their overall academic achievement (He & Zhu, 2019).

In China, where the educational sector has experienced a major digital shift, online learning has become a significant component of the academic system, particularly in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This transition has brought both opportunities and challenges for students, educators, and administrators. In particular, the diverse learning preferences and personalities of students have emerged as important factors influencing their adaptation to online learning. Chinese scholars have been increasingly interested in understanding how these factors interact with the unique cultural and educational dynamics of the country (Zhao et al., 2021). Research in China shows that personality traits can impact not only students' academic performance but also their level of satisfaction and persistence in online learning programs (Chen, 2022).

Focusing on Wenzhou, a city recognized for its educational reforms and innovation, Wenzhou University has implemented a range of online learning initiatives aimed at fostering academic growth and accessibility. The shift to online education at Wenzhou University has created a complex learning environment where students with different personality traits experience and respond to digital education in varying ways. For graduate students, who are often managing multiple academic and personal responsibilities, understanding how personality influences their online learning behaviors is crucial to improving their educational experience. This study explores the impact of personality types on the online learning experiences of graduate students at Wenzhou University, considering factors such as grade level, sex, and major. By examining how students with different personality types engage with online learning, the research aims to uncover significant variations in their learning processes. The findings are intended to provide insights that can help educators, administrators, and students enhance learning efficiency and improve overall academic outcomes in an online environment.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study was to investigate the influence of personality types on the online learning experiences of graduate students at Wenzhou University. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Determine the personality traits among graduate students at Wenzhou University
2. Determine the online learning experiences among graduate students at Wenzhou University

Literature Review

This section presents the related literature which were reviewed by the researchers to gain insight into the conduct of the study.

The COVID-19 pandemic caused a significant shift in learning modalities, presenting challenges in the field of education, particularly

in the delivery of assessments through online platforms. Schools were compelled to invest in new technology and optimize existing resources to remain relevant in the educational sector (Zhu & Liu, 2020). This shift not only redefined traditional education models but also impacted both teachers and students, as online learning introduced new difficulties in maintaining the quality of teaching and assessments (Dhawan, 2020).

Online distance learning offers considerable flexibility for students in terms of how and when they engage with their studies. However, it has influenced key aspects of the teaching-learning process, particularly in areas such as assessment, feedback mechanisms, and the factors that affect online learning effectiveness (Bao, 2020). Assessment is a critical element in education as it allows educators to monitor student progress and track the attainment of learning outcomes prescribed by the curriculum (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020).

Despite the advantages of online learning, such as accessibility of time and place, there are notable drawbacks. The lack of physical interaction among students, for instance, limits opportunities for cooperation and communication, which are important for relieving stress and regulating emotions (Hasan & Bao, 2022). Under these circumstances, exploring the factors that improve online learning efficiency has become a research topic with significant implications for future educational practices (Sun, Tang, & Zuo, 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive correlational research design. A descriptive correlational design is a research approach that combines two key elements: description and correlation. This design is appropriate as it aims to describe the personality traits of graduate students and their online learning experiences, as well as explore the potential relationships between these two variables.

Respondents

The population for this study consisted of graduate students from Wenzhou University in China. This research focused specifically on these graduate students to determine their personality types and their online learning experiences. Graduate students, being older and having more mature and stable psychological and physical conditions compared to undergraduates, provided a more reliable basis for assessing the validity of the research findings.

The study employed stratified random sampling to ensure that a diverse and representative group of graduate students from Wenzhou University is selected. This method involved dividing the population into distinct subgroups (strata) based on characteristics such as grade level, sex, and major. Each subgroup was proportionally represented in the sample, ensuring that the diversity within the graduate student population was captured. Stratified random sampling was particularly appropriate for this study because it allowed for comparisons across various subgroups, ensuring that any variations in online learning experiences linked to personality traits were thoroughly examined.

By using this approach, the study aimed to minimize sampling bias and ensured that the selected participants reflected the broader characteristics of the graduate student population at Wenzhou University. The number of students sampled from each stratum was proportional to the size of that stratum within the overall population. This method enhanced the generalizability of the research findings, ensuring that they were applicable to the wider graduate student body.

To maintain the focus of the research and ensure the integrity of the results, several exclusion criteria were established:

Undergraduate Students: Only graduate students were included in this study. Undergraduate students, who may exhibit different maturity levels and learning behaviors, were excluded to ensure that the findings were specific to the graduate-level population.

Non-Enrolled Students: Students who were not currently enrolled in online courses or have not participated in online learning within the last academic year were excluded, as the study focused on experiences within an active online learning environment.

Incomplete Responses: Participants who did not complete the full survey or interview process were excluded to ensure that all data used in the analysis was comprehensive and reliable.

Non-Consent: Students who did not provide informed consent or withdraw from the study at any point were excluded, in accordance with ethical research practices.

By applying these exclusion criteria, the study ensured a clear focus on the targeted population of graduate students at Wenzhou University who were actively engaged in online learning, thereby enhancing the reliability and relevance of the findings.

Instrument

Data collection was conducted through the use of structured questionnaires. To assess personality traits, a well-established tool such as the Big Five Inventory (BFI) was employed. This instrument measured five core personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. For online learning experiences, a separate questionnaire was developed or adapted from existing instruments to gauge student engagement, satisfaction, self-regulation, and challenges encountered in online learning environments. The survey included Likert scale items to capture a comprehensive view of students' experiences.

Procedure

The first step was the development and pilot testing of a structured survey designed to assess both personality traits and online learning experiences. The survey incorporated validated instruments, such as the Big Five Inventory, and questions specifically tailored to evaluate various aspects of online learning. Upon finalization, the survey was distributed electronically to a representative sample of graduate students at Wenzhou University. To ensure a broad and inclusive sample, a stratified random sampling method was used, taking into account factors such as academic department and year of study. The researcher sought consent from the participants prior to inviting them through email or university communication platforms as respondents of the study.

Upon completion of the survey period, the collected data was compiled and organized for analysis. Responses were anonymized to ensure confidentiality. Statistical analyses, including correlation and regression, was performed to examine the relationships between personality traits and online learning outcomes, such as engagement, satisfaction, and performance.

Data Analysis

Initially, the survey data were cleaned to address any missing or inconsistent responses. This involved checking for completeness, accuracy, and any anomalies that might affect the analysis. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions to summarize both personality traits and online learning experiences. Additionally, correlation analysis (such as Pearson's correlation coefficient) was conducted to determine whether any significant relationships exist between specific personality traits and aspects of online learning, such as engagement or self-regulation.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection of participants' rights and well-being. Before participating, all respondents were provided with a clear explanation of the study's purpose and procedures. They were required to give written informed consent to participate in the survey, interviews, or focus groups. This ensured that participants were fully aware of their involvement and can make an informed decision about their participation. Participants' confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the study. Personal identifiers were removed from survey responses and interview transcripts to ensure anonymity. Data was stored securely and accessible only to authorized research personnel. All electronic data were encrypted, and physical data was kept in locked storage. Participants' privacy were protected by reporting findings in aggregate form, ensuring that individual responses cannot be traced back to specific participants. Participation in the study will be entirely voluntary. Participants were given the right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any negative consequences or loss of benefits. This ensured that their participation was based on their willingness and can be discontinued if they choose. The research design included measures to minimize any potential discomfort or stress for participants. The survey and interview questions was designed to be non-invasive and respectful of participants' experiences and opinions. Additionally, support resources was made available to participants if they experienced any distress related to the study.

The study was submitted for review and approval by the ethics committee of the University of Baguio Graduate School. This review ensured that all ethical standards were met and that the study was conducted in a manner that respects participants' rights and upholds ethical research practices.

Results and Discussion

This section takes into the results of the survey questionnaire of the Graduate students of Wenzhou University gaining their personality types and online learning experiences.

Personality Traits among Graduate Students at Wenzhou University

Graduate students at Wenzhou University were found to exhibit distinct personality traits across the Big Five dimensions. These traits appear to play a substantial role in their online learning experiences, as each personality type aligns with different preferences and capabilities.

Openness

A significant number of respondents demonstrated high levels of openness, as indicated by a majority (59.8%) agreeing with statements such as "I love trying new things" and "I love exploring new ideas" (Questionnaire Item A1). Research suggests that students with high openness are more adaptable to new learning platforms, as they are inherently more curious and open to experiences, which correlates with increased engagement in online learning (Li & Tsai, 2017). This characteristic can enhance students' ability to explore diverse learning materials, take on complex assignments, and actively participate in digital discussions—activities that align with constructivist learning theories, which posit that learning is more effective when students are actively engaged and explorative (Piaget, 1954; Bruner, 1961).

Conscientiousness

Conscientiousness was another prominent trait among the participants, with over 63% reporting high levels of responsibility and organization (Questionnaire Item B4). Conscientious students are typically disciplined, plan-oriented, and self-regulating, all of which

are essential for successful online learning where structured schedules and self-discipline are crucial for managing learning outcomes (He & Zhu, 2019). According to Self-Determination Theory (SDT), students with high conscientiousness feel a strong sense of competence, which increases their motivation and persistence (Ryan & Deci, 2000). This internal drive likely helps conscientious students stay on task, meet deadlines, and achieve high academic outcomes, as observed in similar studies of online learning environments (Chen, 2022).

Extraversion

Responses regarding extraversion were mixed. Although many students (57.84%) reported ease in social situations, a substantial number (41.18%) expressed discomfort with taking central roles in group settings (Questionnaire Item C3). This finding aligns with Eysenck's Personality Theory, which suggests that extraverts may prefer interactive and collaborative environments but can sometimes feel constrained by the solitary nature of online learning (Eysenck & Eysenck, 1985). Extraverted students thrive in group-oriented tasks, so the lack of frequent in-person collaboration could impact their learning satisfaction and engagement. Vygotsky's Social Development Theory also supports this view, emphasizing that social interaction is essential to cognitive development and can be less effectively achieved in virtual learning environments (Vygotsky, 1978).

Agreeableness

High agreeableness was evident, with 63.73% of students showing traits of compassion, trust, and cooperation (Questionnaire Item D2). Agreeable students tend to work well in collaborative settings, and their inclination to help peers may enhance the cooperative aspects of online courses. Agreeableness fosters a supportive online community, reducing the perceived isolation often associated with virtual learning (Chen, 2022). Furthermore, in collaborative online environments, such as discussion forums, agreeable students are more likely to contribute positively, promoting an inclusive learning atmosphere that benefits all participants (Zhao et al., 2021).

Emotional Stability (Neuroticism)

Emotional stability was generally high among respondents, with 62.75% reporting confidence and calmness (Questionnaire Item E5). This stability is essential in online learning contexts, where stressors like technical issues and self-paced schedules can disrupt less emotionally stable students. Emotional stability correlates with lower anxiety levels and a greater ability to manage online learning pressures (Bandura, 1997). In contrast, students high in neuroticism may find it challenging to cope with the uncertainties of online platforms, possibly leading to decreased engagement and persistence in coursework (Xiao & Watson, 2019).

The Big Five model provides a useful framework for understanding how personality traits influence students' adaptation to online learning, with traits such as openness and conscientiousness being especially conducive to self-regulated, virtual education settings. Understanding these personality dynamics can help educators develop tailored support systems that cater to students' specific needs.

Online Learning Experiences among Graduate Students at Wenzhou University

The study also explored students' online learning experiences, highlighting the complexities of engagement, satisfaction, challenges, and adaptability in virtual learning environments.

Engagement and Participation

Approximately 56.86% of students reported active engagement in online discussions and events, while 34.31% struggled to maintain focus (Questionnaire Items A1 and A2). Engagement in online learning is often associated with personality traits like openness and conscientiousness, which foster curiosity and discipline in navigating online coursework. Constructivist theory underscores that active participation leads to deeper learning, as students engage more fully with content when they feel invested and curious (Bruner, 1961). However, the attention-related challenges noted among some respondents suggest that further structural support, such as interactive elements or regular peer interaction, could improve focus and engagement levels.

Satisfaction with Course Quality and Structure

A large proportion of students (63.73%) were satisfied with the structure and organization of online course materials (Questionnaire Item B5). According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), students' satisfaction increases when they perceive online platforms as useful and easy to navigate (Davis, 1989). The organization of course content is particularly important for conscientious students who thrive in well-structured environments. Moreover, the TAM framework suggests that satisfaction drives further engagement, as students are more likely to use and explore a platform they view positively (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

Challenges in Online Learning

While technical difficulties were commonly cited (55.88%), some students (42.16%) also experienced isolation from peers (Questionnaire Items C1 and C5). These challenges align with Cognitive Load Theory, which posits that technical obstacles add extraneous cognitive load, reducing students' capacity to focus on learning (Sweller, 1988). Furthermore, the sense of isolation resonates with extraverted students, who may find the lack of frequent face-to-face interaction limiting. Social Development Theory also suggests that social interaction is crucial to learning, and addressing these feelings of isolation could be essential in improving the online learning experience (Vygotsky, 1978). Potential interventions include structured group work, discussion boards, or synchronous

video sessions to increase social engagement.

Adaptability and Flexibility

Around 70.59% of students appreciated the convenience of online learning, with many feeling they could adjust study habits to accommodate the new format (Questionnaire Item E2). Adaptability is strongly associated with traits like openness and emotional stability, as these students tend to embrace new learning methods and manage stressors well. Self-Efficacy Theory (Bandura, 1997) highlights that students with a sense of control over their learning environment demonstrate higher motivation and persistence. Consequently, these adaptable students may be better positioned to handle the self-directed nature of online learning, balancing academic demands with other responsibilities (Chen, 2022).

Overall, these findings suggest that while many students benefit from the flexibility of online learning, challenges remain, particularly for those who value structured social interactions and technical support. By understanding how personality traits intersect with online learning experiences, educators and administrators can improve course design, offering adaptable learning environments that address students' diverse needs.

Conclusions

The study on personality traits and online learning experiences of graduate students at Wenzhou University highlights the significant influence of personality on students' engagement, satisfaction, and adaptability in online education. Key traits such as openness, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and emotional stability are positively correlated with successful online learning outcomes, while extraversion presents unique challenges due to limited social interaction. Emotional stability emerged as a critical protective factor, fostering resilience in self-directed online environments. These findings underscore the need to adapt online education to accommodate diverse personality-based preferences for optimal learning outcomes.

To address these findings, several actionable recommendations are proposed:

To support extraverted and agreeable students, educators should integrate more interactive elements such as group projects, breakout discussions, and peer feedback sessions. Virtual social events and informal discussion groups can foster a sense of community, mitigating feelings of isolation for students who thrive in social settings.

Institutions should design online courses with clear, logically structured, and easily accessible content, catering to conscientious students who excel in organized environments. Intuitive navigation and regular updates can minimize cognitive load, promoting effective learning for all.

Recognizing that technical issues disrupt engagement, institutions must provide comprehensive technical support, including tutorials, real-time assistance, and routine troubleshooting. A user-friendly interface is essential for a smoother learning experience across all personality types.

Adaptive learning technologies can personalize learning experiences to suit different personality traits. For example, interactive content for extraverted students and structured modules with clear milestones for conscientious learners can increase engagement and satisfaction.

To enhance emotional stability, universities should offer mental health resources, including online counseling, peer mentorship programs, and virtual wellness workshops. These initiatives can address psychological challenges, bolster resilience, and support academic persistence.

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